

Infinite Product Formula Involving Apéry's Constant

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Abstract

We prove an infinite product formula for Apéry's constant $\zeta(3)$ using series involving Riemann zeta functions.

1 Introduction

Apéry's constant $\zeta(3)$ is defined as:

$$\zeta(3) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} \approx 1.202056903159594 \dots$$

Guillera and Sondow [3, Example 5.3] give the following infinite product formula involving Apéry's constant:

$$e^{\frac{7\zeta(3)}{4\pi^2}} = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=0}^n (k+1)^{(-1)^{k+1} \binom{n}{k}} \right)^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2^{n+3}}} = \left(\frac{2}{1} \right)^{\frac{1}{8}} \left(\frac{2^2}{1 \cdot 3} \right)^{\frac{3}{16}} \left(\frac{2^3 \cdot 4}{1 \cdot 3^3} \right)^{\frac{6}{32}} \dots$$

In this paper, we demonstrate another infinite product representation for the mentioned constant through the use of Riemann zeta function series.

Theorem 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
e^{\frac{7\zeta(3)}{2\pi^2}} &= \sqrt{2} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{4k^2 - 1}\right)^{4k^2} \left(1 - \frac{2}{2k + 1}\right)^k \\
&= \sqrt{2} \cdot \left(\frac{4}{3}\right)^4 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{16}{15}\right)^{16} \left(\frac{3}{5}\right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{36}{35}\right)^{36} \left(\frac{5}{7}\right)^3 \cdots \\
&= 1.531547096687457 \dots
\end{aligned}$$

See ([A242908](#)) in the *On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences* (OEIS) [2].

Proof. We consider the following series:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[k \log \left(1 - \frac{1}{2k}\right) - k \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{2k}\right) - 4k^2 \log \left(1 - \frac{1}{4k^2}\right) \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[-2k \left(\operatorname{arccoth}(2k) + 2k \log \left(1 - \frac{1}{4k^2}\right) \right) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

The Taylor series expansion of $\operatorname{arccoth}(x)$ and the natural logarithm function $\log(x)$ are given by:

$$\operatorname{arccoth}(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)x^{2n+1}}, \quad |x| > 1, \quad \log(1-x) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n}, \quad |x| < 1.$$

Therefore, S can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{k^{-2n}}{(n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} - \frac{k^{-2n}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-k^{-2n}}{n \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n}}{(n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n}}{n \cdot 2^{2n}} - \frac{2k^{-2n}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-k^{-2n}}{n(n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n}}{n(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right] \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-k^{-2n}}{(n+1)(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{k^{-2n}}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right].
\end{aligned}$$

We define the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(n)$ as:

$$\zeta(n) = \sum_{k \geq 1} \frac{1}{k^n}, \quad \Re(n) > 1.$$

This expression allows us to transform S into the following sum:

$$S = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{-\zeta(2n)}{(n+1)(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} + \frac{\zeta(2n)}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} \right].$$

Using results from Srivastava and Choi [1, 642, p. 336] and [1, 493, p. 313] respectively, we find

$$-\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(2n)}{(n+1)(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{7\zeta(3)}{2\pi^2}$$

and

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\zeta(2n)}{(2n+1) \cdot 2^{2n}} = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \log(2)).$$

Thus,

$$S = -\frac{\log(2)}{2} + \frac{7\zeta(3)}{2\pi^2}.$$

□

References

- [1] H. M. Srivastava and Junesang Choi, *Introduction and Preliminaries*, in *Zeta and q-Zeta Functions and Associated Series and Integrals*, H. M. Srivastava and Junesang Choi (eds.), Elsevier, London, 2012, pp. 1–140. ISBN: 978-0-12-385218-2
- [2] N. J. A. Sloane et al., The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, published electronically at <https://oeis.org>, 2024.
- [3] J. Guillera and J. Sondow, *Double integrals and infinite products for some classical constants via analytic continuations of Lerch's transcendent*, Ramanujan J. 16 (2008), 243–270.